

UAV-enabled flood damage assessment and recovery monitoring of bridges following Medicane Ianos

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ABSTRACT: Strong winds and heavy rainfall hit western and central Greece on 17–18 September 2020 as the Mediterranean Hurricane (Medicane) “Ianos” made its catastrophic passage through the country. Widespread flooding caused landslides and debris flows, while the erosive forces of water washed away foundation supports and earthworks along swelling rivers, impacting buildings, transport infrastructure, and powerlines. The town of Mouzaki, in Central Greece was one of the hotspots of the event. All five bridges that exist in the area, within a radius of 3 km from the town’s center, suffered extensive damage or complete failure, leading to disruption of transportation and month-long isolation of local communities. The paper presents select outcomes of a comprehensive reconnaissance study where aerial photography and mapping by Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) were used to enhance conventional field investigation and archival research for damage characterization, assessment and recovery. Three dimensional models of select bridge structures are presented and prominent failure patterns are discussed with reference to key response factors and structural characteristics. The paper provides a kaleidoscopic insight into bridge response to a landmark flood event, where the abundance of perishable data was collected in a timely and systematic manner. A universal inadequacy to withstand this flood is identified, raising concerns over what appears to be a new norm of intense weather events in the western Mediterranean. Although the use of UAV mapping in disaster reconnaissance has been common practice in the past years, this is a unique case study where UAVs were also employed for monitoring of bridge recovery in a multi-hazard environment. Comparison of imagery captured at different stages after the event allowed inspection of restorations with minimum human interactions amid the COVID-19 pandemic. Furthermore, it proved useful for the rapid assessment of the impact of a moderate seismic event that affected the damaged structures only a few months after the Medicane. The approach presented provides an effective solution for transport operators managing assets in an environment of increasingly severe and complex hazards.

Keywords: aerial mapping; damage characterization; rapid assessment; recovery; monitoring; natural hazards

1 INTRODUCTION

Remote sensing by Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) is useful for all the three stages of disaster management, as presented by Erdelj et al, 2017, i.e., for pre-disaster preparedness (Stage 1), for disaster assessment (Stage 2), and for disaster response and recovery (Stage 3). UAVs have found applications in the development of early warning systems (Freddi et al., 2021) and in the analysis of risk, e.g., flood risk (Munawar et al., 2021) and resilience of infrastructure systems (Argyroudis et al., 2021).

After a disaster (Stage 2), UAVs are valuable tools for providing situational awareness almost in real time. High resolution measurements of performance indicators, such as displacements and strains, after extreme events, facilitate damage assessment, enhancing visual inspections, and support decision-making by owners and operators (Achilopoulou et al., 2020; Munawar et al., 2022). In Stage 3, UAVs have proven as viable solutions for the generation of digital twins. These can form the base for integrated monitoring, analysis, control, and optimization of infrastructure systems throughout the entire lifecycle. In large scale disasters, optical, but especially infrared images

captured by UAVs help the rescue teams to identify areas requiring immediate rescue operations. Furthermore, the produced geospatial damage maps can guide allocation of compensations and mitigation funds, enhancing the recovery process (Munawar et al., 2022).

UAV-acquired photogrammetric images enable accurate post-disaster reconnaissance and development of 3D models of the target infrastructure (e.g., Greenwood et al., 2019; Valkaniotis et al., 2018; Zekkos, et al., 2018). Thanks to technology advancements, other sensor payloads, such as LiDAR, infrared or hyperspectral cameras, sensors for air quality, or even wireless sensor networks are increasingly deployed.

UAVs are becoming valuable tools due to their relatively low cost, ease of use, and the ability to collect high-quality data remotely and safely (Bray et al., 2019; Wartman et al., 2020; Zekkos et al., 2016). Their use in this study was essential in enabling the rapid collection of perishable data, necessary for the interpretation of failures and the coordination of mitigation actions after an extreme weather event. UAVs enabled exhaustive site reconnaissance and mapping of complex and severely damaged structures, including displaced piers, and collapsed abutments, with increased safety. They by-pass access blockages, due to road failures, enabling mapping of regions that remained isolated for weeks.

Importantly, thanks to the use of UAVs, multiple site investigations were carried out from October 2020 to March 2021, with minimum human interactions, while lockdowns and strict social distancing protocols were in place due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Use of UAVs enabled efficient mapping and allowed remote inspection of the sites by people who could not be on-the-site due to travel restrictions. Furthermore, it resulted in a drastic reduction of inspection times leading to lower exposure of the dispatched team to the current health risks.

2 MEDICANE IANOS

On 17 September 2020, the “Ianos” Mediane struck Greece causing heavy precipitation that exceeded in various locations the mean annual precipitation. It was an extreme weather event, classified as one of the most powerful Mediterranean Cyclones recorded since 1969 (Zekkos et al., 2020). It affected a relatively wide area, extending from the Ionian islands to the eastern coast of the mainland. The maximum daily accumulated values, as measured by the network of automatic meteorological stations of the National Observatory of Athens, reached up to 317 mm (peak recorded in Pertouli) and were among the highest recorded in Greece during the past decade.

The severity and spread of destruction were unprecedented. In the mountainous regions, the

catastrophic consequences of flash flooding included numerous landslides, debris flows, and erosion, impacting buildings, transportation infrastructure, and powerlines. In the low-lying areas of the Thessaly Plain, large scale flooding with the inundation of over 400 km² of agricultural and urban land (Fig. 1a), caused widespread disruptions to communities and severe effects on the economic activity, especially in the city of Karditsa (Fig. 1b).

The town of Mouzaki was harshly impacted. Flash flooding and overflowing of Pamissos river led to widespread erosion of its gabion-protected riverbanks, sweeping away roads, cars (causing one fatality), and riverside structures (Fig. 1c). The area was left without power shortly after the onset of the storm, while all bridges existing within a radius of 3 km from the town’s center, suffered extensive damage or complete failure, resulting in a widespread loss of serviceability of the transportation network.

Figure 1. Photos from Central Greece after the Ianos Mediane: (a) inundated roads in Karditsa; (b) traffic disruptions; (c) structural damage due to extreme erosion and scouring.

3 FIELD RECONNAISSANCE OF DAMAGE TO BRIDGES

A few days after the Mediane, the [US GEER Association](#) deployed an interdisciplinary team of researchers and engineers to collect perishable field performance data from the affected regions. The mission made use of remote sensing technologies, employing optical and satellite imagery, in addition to conventional site characterization and structure inspections. The relevant report (Zekkos et al., 2020)

provides a broad assessment of the medicane impact, based on a systematic collection of field observations and forensic engineering evidence.

A total of 15 bridges were inspected during a reconnaissance field survey conducted in the prefecture of Karditsa. The area covered by this mission and the location of the inspected structures are shown in the map of Figure 2. Damage observations are summarized in Table 1. Three performance levels are defined and associated with relevant damage states: (i) functional bridge: minimum/slight damage, (ii) bridge requiring restoration: moderate, repairable damage, and (iii) failed bridge: severe damage and/or collapse. The adopted color-code uses green, yellow, and red, to indicate damage states (i), (ii), and (iii), respectively.

The spatial distribution of damages (Fig. 2) indicates a significant role played by the ground morphology. Structural failures are concentrated in the mountainous regions, while the bridges of the Thessaly Plain were found structurally unscathed, despite the significant water heights (observe signs of overflowing in Fig.3a), the substantial debris built-up (Fig.3b-c), and the fact that many of these structures are considerably old (30 to over 50 years).

The lowland bridges owe their survival to the flat ground morphology which, naturally, reduced flow velocities and hence the magnitude of erosive actions. Additionally, high plasticity clays, the dominant soil type in the lowlands, are much less erodible than the cohesionless sediments found in Mouzaki.

Table 1. Summary of observed damage to bridges.

No.	Lat., Lon.	Damage state
1	39.17251203, 22.09174728	Slight: Minimal erosion at the abutments
2	39.32248333, 21.79625000	Repairable: Erosion. Partial abutment failure
3	39.34458922, 21.89418983	Minimum: Signs of overflowing
4	39.3485750, 21.90459167	Slight: Overflowing and debris built-up
5	39.34652222, 21.92067222	Slight: Overflowing and debris built-up
6	39.34506944, 21.92634722	Slight: Overflowing and debris built-up
7	39.42734167, 21.92634722	Repairable: Scour and erosion at the abutment. Collapse of approach roadway.
8	39.42580411, 21.66623306	Severe: Scour of mid-pier foundations with considerable settlements.
9	39.40610833, 21.66315000	Collapse: Abutment scour and backfill erosion. Abutment collapse.
10	39.4018440, 21.66842078	Severe: Erosion and partial collapse of abutment/roadway.
11	39.40117261, 21.65286825	Collapse: of consecutive piers and deck segments due to excessive scouring
12	39.30350843, 21.68657321	Severe: Erosion of backfill and collapse of approach roadway.
13	39.30956336, 21.71081606	Repairable: scour and erosion at abutment. Partial collapse of roadway.
14	39.09779247, 21.87822363	Minimum: Overflowing
15	39.47911111, 21.84343611	Minimum: Overflowing

By contrast, in the mountainous regions, W and NW of Karditsa, the level of destruction was extraordinary (Fig. 3d – i). In the town of Mouzaki and the nearby villages, flash flooding and overflowing of Pamissos river led to severe damage or complete failure of a total of seven bridges.

Three characteristic failure patterns were identified, depending on the structural type:

- Single opening bridges showed extensive damage of abutments, with partial or complete wash away of the backfill (Fig. 3f, g, i).
- Structures with piers supported on shallow foundations suffered excessive scouring, leading to deformations (Fig. 3e) and even collapse of middle piers (Fig. 3h).
- Bridges with intermediate supports accumulated substantial debris masses upstream, which contributed to their distress.

Figure 2. Field inspection route with locations of bridges.

4 UAV MAPPING

We deployed a DJI Phantom 4 Professional (P4P) quadcopter to map four damaged bridges of particular interest, namely No. 7, 8, 9 and 11. Field works were conducted on 14 –15 October 2020 (post-flood) and on 16 April 2021, following the Thessaly earthquake sequence discussed in the following. Oblique optical imagery was collected due to the complex geometry of the bridges, and additional aerial photos were captured manually, to eliminate “shadows” and ensure the creation of complete, 3D models.

A total of 3301 photos were captured at flight altitudes ranging from 10–40 m resulting in ground resolution ranging from 0.3 to 1.1 cm/pixel. 60 ground control points were surveyed thoroughly covering the areas mapped, to ensure data quality verification and precise georeferencing of the collected data.

3D models of the bridges (Fig. 4) were created using the Structure-from-Motion technique, as described in Zekkos et al. (2018). A selection of the GCPs was used as check points to assess the quality of the 3D models. Additional manual tie points were initialized to combine autonomous and manual flights' images and reconstruct a unified 3D model. The resulting error estimates ranged from 2.1–4.8 cm with a mean reprojection error for the point cloud at 0.53 pixels.

5 ANALYSIS OF FAILURE MECHANISMS

Based on the developed point clouds (Fig. 4d) we reproduced numerically the failure mechanism of bridge No. 9. This involved the development of a full-height crack on both sides of the concrete wingwalls of the western abutment, which resulted in its breakage, followed by complete wash-away of the backfill and collapse of the roadway (Fig. 4e).

The numerical method, employing Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) analysis of flow–structure interaction and nonlinear mechanical modelling with Finite Elements (FE), is presented in detail in Loli et al.(2022). It is demonstrated that failure is due to

extreme hydrodynamic loads (drag and lift forces) acting on the abutment, during the peak of the flood, as a result of the significant flow velocity and the obstruction of flow caused by the abutment's impermeable, submerged body (Fig. 5a).

Crucially, the numerical study (Loli et al., 2022) highlights that in such bridge typologies, where abutments are located instream, lateral expansion of the channel, due to erosion, leads to an increase of the effective blockage (characterized by the blockage ratio, $BR = B/L$). As shown in Figure 5b, this results in a drastic drop of the structure's tolerance to high flow velocities.

After a parametric investigation using nonlinear finite elements, the study showed that in addition to channel expansion, assumption of a substantially large scour hole, exposing the shallow foundation of the abutment, is necessary to recreate the observed failure through simulations (Fig. 5c–d). As such, it is concluded that, although hydrodynamic loads were the main actors of this failure, scour was certainly a factor that facilitated the complete collapse of the abutment. What is more, scour, rather the lack of it, is the key to the survival of the eastern abutment. The latter remains intact and has been used to support a new Bailey bridge built to replace bridge No. 9.

Figure 3. Photos of bridges in the lowlands of Karditsa: (a) No.3; (b) No. 4; (c) No. 6; and in the mountainous region W and NW of the city: (d) No. 7; (e) No. 8; (f) No. 9; (g) No. 10; (h) No. 11; (i) No.12. See coordinates in Table 1.

Figure 4. 3D point clouds and images of: (a) Mouzaki town center including bridges No. 7 and 8; (b) Photo of bridge No. 7; (c) photo of the settled pier of bridge No. 8; (d) bridge No. 9 and (e) its ruptured western abutment; (f) the collapsed bridge No. 11 and (g) photo of the evidently deformed, remaining middle pier.

For the analysis of the response of bridge No.9, Loli et al. (2022) estimated the minimum flow velocity necessary to inflict the observed failure. The estimated critical value, 7 m/s, is consistent with the great magnitude of erosion that affected the riverbanks of Pamissos, at the location of the bridge, but also downstream, at the center of the town.

The high flow velocities also justify the post-flood condition of bridge No. 11, which is located only 1.5 km upstream of bridge No. 9. Depicted in Figures 3h, and 4f–g, bridge No. 11 is a multi-span, relatively old, structure with piers supported on shallow foundations. The bridge was known to have shown displacements due to scouring before the event, yet remained in service until the evening of 18 September 2020, when it collapsed as a result of this flood. Notably, only one of its three piers was found on site, albeit evidently rotated along both, streamwise and spanwise, directions (Fig. 4g). It was not possible to locate the two missing piers, as well as one segment of the deck, nearby. The fact that they were carried away by the rushing water supports our estimation of high river discharges.

Bridge No. 8 is a similarly old (constructed in the 50s) multi-span structure founded on footings (Fig. 4c). Located approximately 4 km downstream of bridge No. 11, it is estimated that No. 8 was subjected to equally high-intensity flow. Likewise, it has suffered irreparable damage. However, the two bridges

Figure 5. Numerical simulation of the failure of bridge No. 9: (a) CFD analysis of flow – abutment interaction; (b) effect of blockage on hydrodynamic loads; comparison between (c) rapture pattern observed in the field and (d) shear strain localization predicted in the mechanical FE analysis. Adopted from Loli et al (2022).

display quite different failure modes. The schematics of Figure 6 aim to shed some light into the underlying mechanisms of response.

It is well known (Sharify et al, 2013; Qi et al, 2014) that, like abutments, piers pay a price for obscuring the flow: dynamic drag and lift forces develop (Fig. 6a) as a function of water velocity, depending also on the geometric characteristics. While they were subjected to practically similar loads, the two structures deformed quite differently, due to their different structural systems.

No.11 is an isostatic structure, with a deck consisting of simply supported girders. Hydrodynamic loads caused large displacements of its piers, which were supported by scour-compromised, shallow foundations, leading to span unseating, collapse and wash-away. By contrast, the statically indeterminate Gerber bridge (No. 8) showed reduced deck movements, despite sitting on similarly vulnerable foundations. Adequate seating width at the half-joints (highlighted in Fig. 6c) prevented loss of support, while the structure displayed a quite unique failure mechanism, showing practically no rotation of the piers, with over 0.5 m pure settlement of its middle pier. Naturally, strains from the differential displacements of the deck are concentrated on the suspended Gerber girder. It is anticipated that a likely low bearing capacity of the footing (i.e., low factor of safety in vertical loading), in addition to scour, contributed to this failure.

Figure 6. Schematics of (a) pier plan view: flow–pier interaction and observed failure mechanisms in (a) bridge with simply supported girder deck (No. 11) and (c) bridge with continuous (Gerber type) deck (No. 8).

6 MONITORING OF POST-FLOOD RESPONSE AND RECOVERY

6.1 Earthquake sequence following the flood.

A sequence of 3 earthquakes, M_w 6.3; M_w 6.0; and M_w 5.8 (Ganas et al., 2021), shook the region in 10 days, from 3 March–12 March 2021 (6 months after the Mediane). Although the epicenters were estimated relatively far away (about 50 km), concerns rose regarding possible complete failure of bridge No. 8 (Fig. 5c, 6c). Authorities had decided that the latter was unsafe and had to be demolished, yet the bridge was still in place when the earthquake struck.

A UAV was used to capture imagery of the structure and produce a 3D model of its condition after the earthquake. Comparison between pre-quake and post-quake models allowed estimation of relative displacements. For this to be achieved, both models were initially registered based on common GCPs measured during pre and post-quake deployments. Furthermore, the two entities were finely aligned. The ICP registration algorithm was implemented, focusing on unchanged overlapping parts of the two models.

Figure 7 shows the results in terms of relative settlements ($\delta z^{eq} - \delta z^{flood}$). Surprisingly, they are minimal along the entire length of the structure. In a simplified plot of the evolution of settlements, Figure 7a shows that the pier remained stable after the flood, surviving the triple earthquake sequence with no additional deformation. This evidence is reflective of the magnitude of hydrodynamic loads (Fig. 6a) that caused the movement of the pier (by over half meter) during the flood, in comparison to seismic loads (estimated $PGA \approx 0.1$ g), and might prove helpful for future studies dealing with the analysis of this, quite particular, failure mechanism.

6.2 Reinstatement of the damaged highway bridge

No. 7 is a relatively modern motorway crossing of Pamissos river (Fig. 4b). It is a 3-span RC structure with a continuous deck, connected to its 2 middle piers by sliding bearings, while simply sitting upon the abutments. Both the abutments and the piers are supported on piles. The bridge suffered substantial damage (Fig. 3d) primarily concentrated at its western abutment (Fig. 8b). Complete wash-away of the backfill caused loss of support and collapse of the approach roadway. An average height of 2 m of the foundation piles was exposed because of scouring.

We have been monitoring restoration actions that took place on site since their beginning and discussed them in detail, for the purpose of verifying restoration models for flood affected bridges in Mitoulis et al. (2021). The table of Figure 8a shows the progress of the bridge's reinstatement.

Figure 7. Post-flood performance of bridge No. 8: (a) evolution of settlements with reference to the top of the most damaged pier; (b) 3D model of the bridge after the earthquake; (c) contours of seismically induced settlements along the deck.

Days	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60	65
Traffic capacity (%)	0	0	0	0	0	0	50	50	50	50	50	100	100

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 8. Monitoring of the reinstatement of bridge No. 7: (a) evolution of traffic capacity; and photos from the west abutment on (a) the day after the mediane and during the recovery phase, i.e. (c) 35 days and (d) 60 days after the flood.

The bridge was closed for a total of 10 days, during which restoration tasks related to temporary flow altering and debris removal took place. Partial opening to traffic after Day 10 was achieved thanks to reconstruction of the backfill (Fig. 8c) and construction of a temporary approach road. It is worth noting that the approach road was permanently restored later, after day 54, with the construction of an RC slab.

The strategy of splitting restoration tasks in two parts was adopted for the purpose of allowing temporarily undisturbed opening of the motorway to traffic, as soon as possible after the event. Enhancement of the abutment foundation and filling of the scour hole with gabions (Fig. 8c) took place after the partial

reinstatement of the bridge. A photo captured on Day 60 is shown in Figure 8d. When the earthquake struck, bridge 7 was fully restored and did not suffer any additional damage.

7 CONCLUSIONS

A comprehensive reconnaissance study employing UAVs, was carried out in central Greece to document flood induced bridge damages following the passage of the Ianos Mediane. The paper discusses damage patterns observed in a field mission covering the city of Karditsa and the mountainous region W and NW of it. UAV imagery was used to map damages in the town of Mouzaki, which was one of the damage hot spots of the event.

The paper presents 3D models of 4 severely affected river crossing bridges. These models significantly facilitated the identification and analysis of the various failure mechanisms. One was particularly useful in enabling the back-calculation of the flow velocity, an undocumented intensity magnitude of this landmark flood.

Imagery was captured at various times after the Mediane for the purpose of monitoring the recovery of the assets. This proved valuable for the rapid assessment of the impact of an earthquake sequence that shook the region, while mitigation works were underway.

The use of UAVs enabled the timely completion of the investigations and deformation mapping efforts, despite the widespread transportation disruptions due to failures in the local road network. Most importantly, UAVs allowed execution of inspections with minimum of human exposure to health risks, during the peak of the COVID-19 pandemic. The produced 3D models are a powerful visualization tool which was found to fully compensate for the inability to physically visit the site, for the researchers and engineers who could not be present as a result of travel restrictions.

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